

KKSC insertion significance test

Figure S1.

KKSC statistical test. The screening was performed multi-directional for testing any possible tree topology. We tested markers for Petauroidea, Phalangeroidea, and Macropodiformes. Petauroidea+Phalangeroidea shared 61 diagnostic markers, Phalangeroidea+Macropodiformes 26, and Petauroidea+Macropodiformes 19 markers. KKSC didn't derive significance values for hybridization. A bifurcating tree merging Petauroidea and Phalangeroidea reached the highest significance ($p < 2.7 \times 10^{-7}$).